

IMPLEMENTATION OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLES' RIGHTS ACT(R.A.8371) IN SUYO,ILOCOS SUR

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This study was conducted to determine the Implementation of Indigenous People's Rights Act of 1997 in Suyo, Ilocos Sur.

The following are the salient findings of the study:

.The Local government unit officials have a “High” level of Administrative Capability. All the components namely Personnel Capability, Financial Capability and Leadership Capability obtained High level.

As a whole the implementation of the IPRA in Suyo, Ilocos Sur along government Initiative is “High”.

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. The local government officials have a high capability in implementing government initiative along IPRA.
2. The government initiatives along the IPRA are highly implemented.

With the foregoing findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The local government unit officials should; Help the Bagos preserve their cultural identity and instill in the minds and hearts and to other residents to respect the Bagos and educate them through research studies .
2. The local government unit officials should clearly explain to the Bagos the need and importance for them to be educated to be aware of their rights and privileges and to uplift their social, economic ,political and spiritual standing .
3. The Bagos should avail of every opportunity initiated by the government as to be integrated in the mainstream of the society and realize that they are part in every programs and projects of the government.

KEYWORDS:*IPRA,RIGHTS,INDIGENOUS,BAGOS and ADMINISTRATIVE CAPABILITY*

Introduction

There had been many changes in our attitude towards the indigenous people, that are usually found in the hinterland places of the country. During the times of the Spaniards in the country they were not reached by the Spaniards for they isolated themselves in the mountains, where they could hardly be reached to continue their practices and beliefs.

In 1973 the constitution started to mention and give recognition to them as minority in the country. In the 1987 Philippine Constitution they were recognized and given special treatment. The clear intent, in the context of the Constitution viewed in its entirety, is to create an exception to uniformity of treatment under law mandated under the standard of “equal protection of the laws”. Meaning the indigenous people be part of the social mainstream and given equal access to every political, social, economic, cultural, and spiritual or religious development. This integration and recognition was clearly spelled-out in the Indigenous People’s Rights Act of 1997 (IPRA). To this end, the state shall protect the rights of indigenous cultural communities to their ancestral lands to ensure their economic, social, and cultural well-being. Their recognition is subjected to national development policies and programs. The IPRA of 1997 includes the (13) critical aspects that enumerate the following: a) general provisions b) definition of terms c) right to ancestral domain d) right to self-governance and empowerment e) social justice and human rights f) cultural integrity, g) National Commission on Indigenous People’s NCIP, h) delineation and recognition of ancestral domain, i) jurisdiction and procedures for enforcement of rights, j.) ancestral domains fund, k) penalties, l) merger of office of Northern Cultural Communities (ONCC) and the Office of Southern Cultural Communities (OSCC), and m) final provisions.

Bagos can be found in the hinterland municipalities in Region I. They are a mixture of the Cordilleran and the lowland people. Bagos are settled in sixteen (16) municipalities of Ilocos Sur, ten (10) municipalities of La Union and two (2) municipality in the province of Pangasinan.

The Bagos will benefit from the study by improving their cultural, social, economic and belief system whether it be political, spiritual or religious. The Local government will be able to access information regarding them that will be the basis of implementing plans for the local community and the whole indigenous population in the country. Education-wise the implementers and planners will be able to find mechanisms to integrate them and empower their being and personality.

This study determined the implementation of IPRA in Suyo, Ilocos Sur, the assistance that the local government unit provides to improve their plight.

Statement of the Problem

This study was conducted to determine the implementation of the Indigenous People’s Rights Act of 1997 (IPRA) in Suyo, Ilocos Sur.

1. What is the level of administrative capability of the LGU officials along the following.
 - a)leadership capability,
 - b) personnel capability, and
 - c)financial capability?

2. What is the level of implementation of the IPRA in Suyo, Ilocos Sur in terms of the following?
 - a) ancestral domain,
 - b) ancestral lands,
 - c) right to stay in territories,
 - d) right in case of displacement,
 - e) right to regulate entry of migrants,
 - f)right to safe and clean water,
 - g)right to claim parts of reservations,
 - h) right to resolve conflict,
 - i) right to participate in decision-making,
 - j) freedom from discrimination and right to equal opportunity and Treatment,
 - k) right to religious, cultural sites, and ceremonies,
 - l)right to indigenous knowledge systems and practices and to develop own science and technologies, and
 - m) access to biological and genetic resources

Research Methodology

This section presents the research design, population and sample, data gathering procedures, instruments used and statistical treatment of data.

The procedures was followed by the researcher in the conduct of this study which is presented in this section.

Research Design. This study employed the descriptive method of research to determine the level of implementation of the Indigenous People’s Rights Act 1997 (IPRA).

Population and Sample. The respondents of this study were the Bagos , that are identified and was retrieved from the listing of the National Commission of Indigenous People Region I office tallied with the listing of the LGU on Bago residents. The Slovin’s formula was used to compute the number of Bago residents.

Data-Gathering Instrument. The questionnaire was the main data gathering instrument.

The researcher used questionnaire and interview as the main tools for data gathering. The items in the questionnaire were sourced by the researcher from books, journals, magazines, theses, dissertations and interviews from the prospective respondents.

To determine the validity and reliability of the tool, the first draft of the questionnaire was presented to the researcher’s adviser, then to His experts to determine whether these are comprehensible and can be easily answered by the target respondents. The researcher subjected it to dry run among the Bagos of Sta.Cruz, Ilocos Sur. Some of the Validators were officials of National Commission on Indigenous People Region I office, Mr. Felinor Sajonia then the Regional Director of NCIP Region I and Mayor Samuel B. Subagan Jr. of Suyoy, Ilocos Sur, also a Bago member, who are deemed experts on the study.

Data-Gathering Procedure. The researcher used the five (5) point scale in the measurement of the items in the questionnaire for the easy understanding of the target respondents as they accomplished the said questionnaire. Thus, the following scale counts were employed:

To determine the government initiatives for the indigenous

Statistical Limit	Symbol	Descriptive Rating
4.21 – 5.00	Very Highly Capable	VHC
3.41 – 4.20	Highly Capable	HC
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Capable	MC
1.81 – 2.60	Slightly Capable	SC
1.00 – 1.80	Very Slightly Capable	VSC

To determine the level of implementation of the Indigenous People’s Rights Act (IPRA):

Statistical Limit	Symbol	Descriptive Rating
4.21 – 5.00	VHI	Very Highly Implemented
3.41 – 4.20	HI	Highly Implemented
2.61 – 3.40	MI	Moderately Implemented
1.81 – 2.60	SI	Slightly Implemented
1.00 – 1.80	VSI	Very Slightly Implemented

Statistical Treatment of Data. The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data that were gathered in the study.

1. The mean to present the descriptive statistics of this study.

Theoretical Framework

This study on the implementation of the Indigenous People’s Rights Act of 1997 in Suyo, Ilocos Sur is premised primarily on the provision of the Philippines constitution as follows: Article 4, Section 22 states that the “state recognizes and promotes the rights of indigenous cultural communities within the framework of national development.”

In the same vein, Article 10, Section 17 also states that the state recognizes, respects and protects the rights of indigenous cultural communities to preserve and develop their cultures, traditions and institutions, and shall consider these rights on the formulation of national plans and policies.

Similarly Article IV Section 17 also provides that the state recognizes, respects and protects the right of indigenous cultural communities to preserve and develop their cultures. traditions and institutions. It shall consider these rights on the formulation of national plans and policies. Furthermore, Section 18, Paragraph 2 further states that the state shall encourage and support researchers and studies in the arts and culture. (Nolledo, 1994).

Basic consideration on policy formulation on the government sector in the context of development planning process is the integration of programs and projects that are acceptable to the existing culture, practices, values, beliefs and standard norms of the majority of the people in a given time. Such program policies are responsive to their basic needs and aspirations. This accepted conventional principle is envisioned in Republic Act 837 otherwise known as “The Indigenous Peoples Right Act of 1997” which provides that the “state recognizes its obligation to respond to the strong expression of the indigenous people (ICCs/IPs) for cultural integrity by assuring maximum participation on the direction of education, health as well as other services of ICCs/IPs in order to render such services more responsive to the needs and desires of these communities.

Rights to Self-Governance and Empowerment

The State shall recognize, respect and protect the rights of ICCs/IPs to preserve and develop their cultures, traditions and institutions. It shall consider these rights on the formulation of national laws and policies.

Fraiser’s (2007) study investigated on the Manobo’s response, highlighting their adaptive shifts in their social organization to withstand outside forces – the appearance of organizations seeking secure land rights, and the possible causal mechanisms that may have triggered these changes. A major finding is that the Manobo’s coordinated efforts to withstand pressures from the dominant society originated in the religious domain. He concluded that the emergence and effectiveness of Manobo organizations has often been hindered by government favoritism toward loggers and settlers, the long standing enemies of natural forests.

Implementation of Education of the Bagos

Juan (2008) noted the various manifested effects of the cultural practices on the education of minority groups. These are among others the: 1. Formal education in the: a) public secondary school; 2) alternative learning system training programs on: a) literacy-reading, writing and numeracy; b) basis education for adults and out-of-school youth; c) preschool education of young children; d) “catching up” programs for school dropouts; e) health education/better health practices; f) agriculture education; g) trade and union education; h) nutrition/better and nutrition food intake; and, i) waste management and disposal; and, 30 developing skills in: a) communication; b) problem-solving; c) critical thinking; and, d) learning to learn.

Social Integration of the Bagos

Cortez (2003) underscored the various community projects and activities where most cultural minority groups are involved; They are shy; 2. They refrain from joining cultural activities; 3. They manifest difficulty in teaching with others; 4. They hardly understand the meaning of community development; 5. They do not have the patience to: a) attend community meetings; b) contribute their opinion on specific community project ; c) participate in discussions/brainstorming ; d) wait for results; 6. They have the eerier feeling of being ostracized.

Problems on the Social Integration of the Bagos

Hidalgo (2004) noted the problems that the local government unit officials encounter as they do their best to assist the cultural minority residents to integrate themselves in the social mainstream in their respective communities: 1. Most Bagos are shy; 2. They prefer not to interact with others; 3. They are not interested in joining community activities; 4. They fear that their cultural practices will be overshadowed by new lifestyle; 5. Some of them are uncooperative; 6. They are not open to new learning or trends; 7. They abhor activities relative to other religions; 8. They fear that community activities will incur expenses; 9. They have their own religious festivities; and, 10. They have social maladjustment features further stated. The complex problem of the vulnerability of Filipino OSY has attracted attention from many other organizations. In a study performed by the World Bank (WB), focus groups and questionnaires created a profile for an average Filipino OSY, which helps to understand their vulnerability, according to Abrenich (2002). The World Bank (WB) study indicated that the majority of the OSY live in environment with few livelihood options where asset attainment is difficult. Economic conditions, social conditions of the family, and personal qualities all contribute to the high prevalence of OSY in the Philippines. As expected the study showed that Out-of-School Youth are typically born to large impoverished families whose household heads also lack basic education skills. The families' lack of financial resources was ultimately responsible for forcing youth out of school, Abrenich stated.

Often children are required to work to support parents and younger siblings. This is particularly true for the 15-24 age groups who often have to quit school to help their parents sought employment. About 1/5 of the WB focus groups' participants came from single-parent families, or the family's sole wage earner was either ill or ailing. Often in these cases, the youth take responsibility of finding a source of income to provide for the family. Most OSY generally have parents who work in unskilled jobs resulting from a low level of education. Typically in two-parent households, the father's job was often low-paying and self or seasonally employed, Abrenich further noted.

RESULTS/FINDINGS

Table 1 Item Mean Ratings Showing the Level of Administrative Capability of the Local Government Unit Officials along Leadership Capability

RESULTS/FINDINGS

Items	BAGO RESIDENTS	
		DR
1. Sets the mission and vision of the LGU as regards the 1997 IPRA.	3.78	HC
2. Plans, organizes and directs all projects and activities for the indigenous residents.	3.74	HC
3. Ensures that all employees/persons involved in projects/activities for the indigenous residents do/accomplish their tasks.	3.63	HC
4. Encourages active participation of all stakeholders and other community residents in all projects/activities for the indigenous.	3.68	HC
5. Practices fairness and sobriety in leading and instructing participants in the implementation of the all projects/activities for the indigenous residents.	3.56	HC
6. Establishes linkages and harmonious relations with other agencies.	3.53	HC
7. Makes wise decisions and resolve problems based on correct and relevant information.	3.66	HC
8. Has knowledge and understanding of governing the community.	3.63	HC
9. Has credibility in the Municipality.	3.70	HC
10. Encourages participation of constituents in prioritizing barangay projects.	3.73	HC

11. Practices transparency in various financial transactions.	3.76	HC
12. Has understanding of his own role.	3.72	HC
13. Has ability to source out funds.	3.69	HC
14. Has good leadership attitudes	3.68	HC
15. Has sufficient management abilities.	3.67	HC
Overall	3.66	H

The table shows that local government unit officials have a “High” level of leadership capability (3.66). The item “Sets the mission and vision of the LGU as regards the IPRA of 1997” obtained the highest mean rating of 3.78 which is described as “Highly Capable.” On the other hand, the item “Establishes linkages and harmonious relations with other agencies” obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.53 which is also described as “Highly Capable.” It shows that in all items, the Local Government were Highly Capable, which implies that the Local Government unit officials are all educated, trained and aware of their responsibility even to the marginalized sector in their society.

Table 2 Item Mean Ratings Showing the Level of Administrative Capability of the Local Government Unit Officials along Personnel Capability

Items	BAGO RESIDENTS	
		DR
Personnel		
1. Strict compliance and implementation of 1997 IPRA	3.85	HC
2. Prioritizing implementation of frontline services to indigenous residents	3.73	HC
3. Actualize step-by-step procedures at all times	3.53	HC
4. Officer/employee responsible for each step is identified and held accountable	3.81	HC
5. Ordinances enacted ensure the benefits of the indigenous residents	3.66	HC
6. Capacity to enact ordinances to address the current issues and concerns of the indigenous residents	3.63	HC
7. Capacity to enact ordinances that are both for urgent concerns and long – term benefits for the indigenous residents.	3.63	HC
8. Capacity to make resolutions for the indigenous residents that are beneficial for them on urgent issues and for long – term application.	3.90	HC
Overall	3.72	H

The high level of personnel capability could be attributed to the willingness of the local government unit to implement the Act in Suyo, because their respect to their ancestors, rich heritage, and culture, and until the moment they are highly populated with Indigenous People. The average mean of 3.72 indicates that they are highly capable in the actualization step-by-step procedures at all times because of the trainings, seminars, and experience of the LGU officials.

Table 3

Item Mean Ratings Showing the Level of Administrative Capability of the Local Government Unit Officials along Financial Capability

Items	BAGO RESIDENTS	
		DR
1.Ensures the availability of adequate funds to support all projects and activities for the indigenous residents	3.73	HC
2. Ability to search for financial support from other sources	3.50	HC
3. Sustains the fair allocation of funds	3.55	HC
4. Skillful and competent in budget management	3.60	HC
5. Observes transparency, as well as check and balance in disbursement of funds	3.54	HC
6. Balance sheets, spread sheets and auditing report are always updated and ready for scrutiny	3.66	HC
Overall	3.60	H

The table reveals that local government unit officials have a “High” level of financial capability (= 3.60). The item “Ensures the availability of adequate funds to support all projects and activities for the indigenous residents” obtained the highest mean rating of 3.75 which is described as “Highly capable.” On the other hand, the item “Ability to search for financial support from other sources” got the lowest mean rating of 3.50 which is also described as “Highly capable.” The high level of capability on finances is because of the competent budget management and availability of adequate funds to support all projects and activities for the indigenous residents. It further implies that the government is in full support of the integration of the indigenous people in the social mainstream.

Table 4 Mean Ratings Showing the Level of Implementation of the IPRA in Suyo, Ilocos Sur

Government Initiatives	BAGOS	
		DR
A. Ancestral Domain	3.58	HI
B. Ancestral Lands	3.76	HI
C. Right to Stay in Territories	3.56	HI
D. Right in Case of Displacement	3.57	HI
E. Right to Regulate Entry of Migrants	3.57	HI
F. Right to Safe and Clean Water	3.54	HI
G. Right to Claim Parts of Reservations	3.56	HI
H. Right to Resolve Conflict	3.73	HI
I. Right to Participate in Decision-Making	3.68	HI
J. Freedom from Discrimination and Right to Equal Opportunity and Treatment	3.73	HI
K. Right to Religious, Cultural Sites and Ceremonies	3.70	HI
L. Right to Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices and to Develop Own Science and Technologies	3.86	HI
M. Access to Biological and Genetic Resources	3.90	HI
As a Whole	3.67	HI

As shown in the table, there is a “High” (= 3.67) level of implementation of the IPRA in Suyo, Ilocos Sur. The indicator “Access to Biological and Genetic Resources” obtained the highest mean rating of 3.90 which is described as “High.” On the other hand, the indicator “Right to Safe and Clean Water” obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.54 which is also described as “High.” It means that they are given the rights to appreciate and use their flora and fauna and that they care for their environment, also to their bodies of water, as one source of their livelihood.

Conclusions

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The local government officials have a high capability in implementing government initiatives along IPRA.
2. The government initiatives along the IPRA are highly implemented.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions the following are recommended.

1. The local government unit officials should; Help the Bagos preserve their cultural identity and instill in the minds and hearts and to other residents to respect the Bagos and educate them through research studies .
2. The local government unit officials should clearly explain to the Bagos the need and importance for them to be educated to be aware of their rights and privileges and to uplift their social, economic ,political and spiritual standing .
3. The Bagos should avail of every opportunity initiated by the government as to be integrated in the mainstream of the society and realize that they are part in every programs and projects of the government.

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